

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in energy povERTy

D5.1 Terms of reference of Open Call including evaluation criteria

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Report information

Purpose of the Report	Sum the available pack of documentation in English with all the information on the call, the evaluation criteria and the mentorship programme cycle		
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ABOUT ASSERT

The ASSERT project is a European initiative under the LIFE23-CET-ENERPOV framework, which will address the critical issue of energy poverty, particularly among physically disabled persons. The project goal is three-fold:

1. Ensure that policy makers at all levels of administrations, as well as energy practitioners and advisors are trained on energy matters, including on topics related to energy poverty, taking into consideration the multidimensional aspects of energy poverty and context of clean energy transition.
2. Roll-out programmes to train front line workers in energy poverty and green energy solutions. Front-line workers addressed in those programmes should include health and social care workers or other professionals who can help identify households affected and provide them with advice and information on solutions to reduce energy consumption and access more affordable and innovative sources.
3. Offer targeted training courses for energy-poor households affected by energy poverty, including those with low digital skills. Such courses should enhance the energy and digital literacy awareness of households affected by energy poverty, enable them to better control their energy bills and participate actively in the clean and just energy transition.

ASSERT will focus on persons with physical disabilities who have higher energy needs and lower income and therefore are more susceptible to energy poverty and its effects. Addressing their needs can interrupt the vicious circle of aggravating health conditions as a consequence of unhealthy household conditions due to energy poverty.

The project will deliver an integrated target-specific training and mentorship programme for local policymakers and intermediaries, and will equip them with essential skills and knowledge and support to implement sustainable energy solutions, while integrating energy poverty considerations into broader policy frameworks.

ASSERT consortium

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	AISFOR SRL	AISFOR SRL	IT
2	RETE ASSIST - ETS	RETE ASSIST - ETS	IT
3	ENERCOOP	ENERCOOP	FR
4	ASOCIACION ECOSERVEIS	ECOSERVEIS	ES
5	CITIZEN CROSSROADS	CCR	EL
6	ENERGEIAKO GRAFEIO KYPROU	CEA	CY
7	CLIMATE ALLIANCE - KLIMA-BUENDNIS - ALIANZA DEL CLIMA e.V.	CLIMATE ALLIANCE	DE
8	EUROPEAN NETWORK ON INDEPENDENT LIVING BRUSSELS OFFICE	ENIL	BE
9	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
10	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENERGY AND CLIMATE POLICY STICHTING	IEECP	NL
11	ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO	Eurac	IT

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Executive summary

In this document the approach to develop the key documents for the ASSERT call for mentorship is presented - as foreseen under the framework of the ASSERT project.

General information about the structure of the Mentorship itself is provided and additional details on the design of the documents and key decision taken.

The documents which constitute the ASSERT Call for Mentorship Programme (detailed herewith and attached) are the following:

- **ASSERT MENTORSHIP ToR (Terms of Reference):** call document to provide practical details to potential participants on how to submit the request to adhere to the mentorship programme.
- **ASSERT APPLICATION FORM:** form to be filled in to submit a request for the mentorship – the form is provided both online (the form to be duly filled in and submitted) and an offline version to facilitate the preparation of the request
- **Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs):** a document with the answers to the frequently asked questions available for all the applicants for transparency

The full package has been prepared in English and further translated / adapted in each language where the mentorship call is launched (Cyprus, French, Greece, Italian, Spanish)

1. Mentorship structure

The pilot activities within the ASSERT project are framed within a mentorship programme for municipalities and intermediaries. The mentorship programme will be implemented in the 5 project countries – Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy and Spain and with 5 pairs of municipality-intermediary in each country. The selection of the 5 pairs will be the outcome of the “ASSERT Mentorship Call”.

With the selected pairs, the experts’ partners will provide **direct and customised mentorship** to **fill in the knowledge and capacity gaps** by supporting them respectively in their activities in the policy design (municipalities) and on the ground (intermediaries). The outcomes jointly designed of the 20 mentorship programmes, such as the target-specific **training** and **policy and practical tools**, will then be made fully accessible to provide support to a wider audience of local governments.

The mentorship is structured in a series of different steps – which include at least the following common actions:

- Identify the knowledge gaps
- Participate in the co-design of specific training material
- Engage other colleagues in the training process
- Assess the socio-political context through specific interviews with the final beneficiaries
- Implement specific support actions with the intermediaries (customized per pilot country)
- Monitor and evaluate the beneficiaries’ condition after the implementation of the different actions

Figure 1 - Mentorship structure

The access to the mentorship is through a fair and transparent process developed as an open call for proposals.

2. Open call for mentorship preparation

Climate Alliance lead the preparation of the open call for the ASSERT mentorship programme by drafting (in English) the following documents:

- **ASSERT MENTORSHIP ToR (Terms of Reference):** document designed to provide practical details to potential participants on how to submit the request to adhere to the mentorship programme.
- **ASSERT APPLICATION FORM:** the application form to be filled in to reply to the mentorship call and submit a request – the form is provided both online (the form to be duly filled in and submitted) and an offline version to facilitate the preparation of the request
- **FAQs:** a document with the answers to the frequently asked questions to be available for all the applicants for transparency

In order to take into consideration national contexts, each piloting partner customized the Term of Reference (an example is the description of the mentorship services which vary in each National ToR as it depends on the expertise of the piloting partner and the local specificities).

Once the English version was approved, it was translated / adapted in the languages of all pilot countries – French, Greece (also a version for Cyprus was provided), Italian and Spanish (Catalan).

All documents are available at a dedicated link both on the project website ASSERT (www.assertacademy-eu) and on the website of each partner organization.

2.1 ASSERT Mentorship Programme call - Terms of Reference (ToR)

The ASSERT MENTORSHIP ToR document is divided in seven chapters providing comprehensive information about the call as well as information on the project. The contents of the chapters are described below:

Chapter 1 provides information about ASSERT and the overall objective of the project.

Chapter 2 provides a general introduction to the nexus between energy poverty and people with physical disabilities.

Chapter 3 details the mentorship process and what it constitutes.

Chapter 4 focuses on the application form format and provides supporting information on how to fill the different sections.

Chapter 5 provides additional information about the evaluation.

Chapter 6 mentions how the data contained in the proposals will be processed (GDPR).

Chapter 7 presents how to submit additional questions.

Chapter 8 details on the agreement with awarded proposals

2.1.1 Chapter 1 – information about ASSERT

The first chapter, common to all pilots aims to increase understanding about the overall framework of the projects, key objectives and long-term goals.

2.1.2 Chapter 2 – nexus between energy poverty and people with physical disabilities

Considering that for many applicants it is expected that the nexus between energy poverty and people with physical disabilities is a new topic, it was agreed to include an informative section to provide a first understanding about what are the core elements of the mentorship and the reason to specifically address this topic.

2.1.3 Chapter 3 – mentorship process

In the third chapter the description of the mentorship process is introduced entering into details for each phase.

Figure 2 - Mentorship Process

In detail three phases were identified:

- *Pre-application*: with informative sessions to facilitate the access to the call for different municipalities. On top of the webinars organized by each pilot it should be considered as part of the pre-application process also activities performed under WP4 as, during the interview with different local governments, to understand their need, specific mention was done to the upcoming call in order to increase awareness and interest.
- *Application*: in all the countries the call started the 3rd of February and should end the 16th of March. Extension to the deadline could be evaluated but, in case, an extension is considered needed even if only for one country, all the others will have to extend the deadline.
- *Co-design*: together with the mentorship constitute already a key activity. During this phase, the paid or local governments and local intermediary will work more strictly with the mentors to fine tune their actions and increase their capacities.
- *Mentorship*: it is the natural follow-up of the co-design phase where the experts will still support the beneficiaries but in a less intense way leaving them to proceed with more autonomy.

It is specifically in this chapter that each pilot had the opportunity to customize their term of reference providing concrete examples of possible requests.

For example, France proposed as examples:

- The development of an awareness campaign
- Exchange of good practice and replication of activities from similar context
- Training on how to approach the energy poverty topic and support vulnerable consumers.
- Increase awareness on specific financial mechanism in France (SLIME)
- Support to apply for the SLIME program with a focus on people with disabilities
- Etc.

2.1.4 Chapter 4 – application form

In this chapter there is integrative information to combine with the application form and that can guide the applicants to develop a stronger proposal. More details about the application form are in the dedicated section 2.2.

2.1.5 Chapter 5 – evaluation process

For transparency, the evaluation process and especially the evaluation criteria are shared in the Term of Reference.

The established criteria of evaluation are common to all the pilot countries. However, each country will be evaluated separately considering that, for the structure of the project itself, the aim is to support 5 projects in each country.

The evaluation criteria were carefully designed in order to balance the need for a transparent comparison with the aim to not penalize projects submitted by local governments with less or zero experience.

The first mandatory request is that the proposal is submitted by two entities: a local government and an intermediary organization. This is the only criteria that if not respected result in the complete rejection of the proposal.

Once the proposal is considered eligible the score is determined by two main areas:

- Partnership
- Specific request

The **partnership** is evaluated with 3 elements each adding 1 point, if satisfied. In detail the aim is that in the proposal it is clear the type of partnership between the two applicants and the fact that they will work jointly. One additional point is granted in case the intermediary organization is a Disabled People Organization (DPO). In fact, for ASSERT, it is particularly important to work directly with organizations coordinated by disabled people. A third point is granted in case the applicants are able to provide more information about on-going collaboration with other local stakeholders that can reinforce the achievements of the project.

The **specific request** is evaluated differently, with a score from 1 to 7 and refers directly to the quality of the proposal, capacity to reach the beneficiaries and future sustainability. As mentioned before, considering ASSERT aims to also support local governments that are just starting to address these challenges, the evaluation is based more on the quality of the request than on the specific content.

Overall, the minimum score possible is 1 and the maximum 10.

The Term of reference provides some additional information about the expected commitment in case the proposal is awarded. This section was included in order to make sure that the local governments and intermediary organisations are aware that the experts will support them but it is expected of their commitment to perform the activities.

2.1.6 Chapter 6 – data protection

In this chapter it is detailed how the data provided in the submission will be used.

2.1.7 Chapter 7 – FAQ

Applicants have the opportunity to ask additional questions and support for the preparation of the proposal. Each country will address separately the different questions received and make public the answer.

2.1.8 Chapter 8 – Details of agreement

During the preparation of the term of reference, it was considered key to have a chapter to provide additional information about the needed commitments from the applicants during the mentorship process. Some information about the agreement expected to be signed among the parties, if awarded, is provided. The objective is to make sure that applicants are aware of the specific requirements. Some pilot countries decided to not include this specific chapter based on their experience with local government. In that case they preferred either to mention more specifically the requirements during the informative sessions (webinar) or to leave the discussion only with the awarded beneficiaries.

2.2 Assert application form

The Application form was first developed in word with the aim to provide the applicants a document that can be filled off-line. The exact same structure was then uploaded online (developed on EU SURVEY). Each piloting country decided to develop a separate online application form in order to facilitate access to the different proposals by the evaluators and make sure that, in case someone sends questions, these are addressed by the right reference person for the country.

The application form is divided in three sections:

- Organizations
- Partner sections
- Mentorship request

Organizations focus on the administrative information of the two applicants. It includes a section to better understand their background and experience. However, as mentioned before, this section is not scored in order to do not penalize realities with less experience.

The **partner sections**, scored, focus on how the two partners will work together and how they aim to engage other stakeholders and the beneficiaries.

The **mentorship request**, scored, is the core section of the application form and is where the applicants have the chance to provide additional information about their specific request.

For each section character limit are set to give a specific framework to the applicants and to make sure the application is designed in an effective way to collect key information but without burdening the applicants with a long process for submission.

To support the analysis of the WP4 it was agreed to add a final section for the applicants to provide a **self-evaluation** of their expertise. This is clearly not scored and simply used internally to develop further the gap analysis and better design the training.

2.3 FAQs

The package of documents of the call for mentorship includes also a document with the most frequent questions. This document was originally drafted with some expected questions and will be updated (on a country level) with new questions to guarantee that all interested applicants receive the same answer.

3. Open call promotion - webinars

Each pilot country organized a minimum of one webinar to present the call and directly reply to questions from the participants. Each webinar was also registered and made available on-line for other interested applicants. The webinars were held in the following days:

Table 1 - Open Call webinars dates

Country	Date
Cyprus	28/01/25
France	10/02/2025
Greece	21/02/2025
Italy	14/02/2025
Spain	05/12/2025 (in Catalan), 12/02/2025 (in Spanish)

To guarantee alignment in the messages a basic set of slides were designed for each partner to translate, further modified to provide more information about energy poverty and the specific nexus between energy poverty and physical disability in each country.

ANNEX I – Term of Reference in English

ASSERT MENTORSHIP REQUEST

*Access to support from the ASSERT team
to tackle energy poverty affecting people with physical disability*

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1. Introduction

The present document provides additional support to the organisations looking to apply for the mentorship provided under the framework of ASSERT project. The full documentation and information for the call are available on the website (LINK).

[Chapter 1](#) provides information about ASSERT and the overall objective of the project.

[Chapter 2](#) provides a general introduction to the nexus between energy poverty and people with physical disabilities.

[Chapter 3](#) enters into details about the mentorship and what it constitutes. Please review carefully the section for key information.

[Chapter 4](#) focuses on the application form format and provides supporting information on how to fill the different sections.

[Chapter 5](#) provides additional information about the evaluation.

[Chapter 6](#) mentions how your data in the proposals will be processed (GDPR).

[Chapter 7](#) presents how it is possible to submit additional questions.

To prepare a successful proposal it is advisable to download all the documents in advance from the website.

The estimated time to complete the application form is 8 working hours.

2. About ASSERT

ASSERT project sets the stage for transformative action on energy poverty.

Large-scale multiactor training and mentorship programme to ASSist people with physical impairments in enERgy poverTy - **ASSERT**

The ASSERT project, **awarded** under the LIFE23-CET- ENERPOV framework, primarily addresses the **nexus between energy poverty and physically disabled persons**. The project aims to provide essential knowledge, competencies, and skills to key actors, such as policymakers, intermediaries, and directly affected persons, ensuring they can address energy poverty and mitigate its impacts.

Grounded on an understanding of the complex, intersecting challenges physically disabled persons face; ASSERT approach emphasizes the importance of a targeted, inclusive response. The aim is to address three different target groups: **policy actors, intermediary/actors** on the ground and **people directly affected**. Reinforcing the knowledge and capacity of all the stakeholders and promoting strong joint collaboration it will be possible to ensure no one is left behind in the transition to clean energy. Practically during the project, local policymakers and intermediaries have access to dedicated training and mentorship. Thanks to the increased skills and knowledge, there will be the chance to implement sustainable energy solutions while integrating energy poverty considerations into broader policy frameworks.

ASSERT will undertake a series of activities, beginning with **research on the nexus** between the two project dimensions. ASSERT will select 25 realities (targeting municipalities and intermediaries in Italy, Spain, France, Cyprus and Greece) with which it will undertake a **direct and customised mentorship** aiming at **filling their knowledge and capacity gaps** and supporting them respectively in their activities on the ground and in the policy design. The **training** jointly designed will then be made accessible to a wider audience to provide support to more local governments.

Figure 3 - Annex Mentorship structure

3. Nexus between Energy Poverty and physical disabilities

Energy poverty is a growing social phenomenon which refers to the situation in which households are unable to access essential energy services and products. In many cases, energy poverty is driven by 3 underlying root causes: high energy expenditure in proportion to the household budget, low levels of income, and low energy performance of buildings and appliances.

However, energy poverty is a **multidimensional issue with wide-reaching implications** on various aspects of individuals' lives, including economic stability, social inclusion, health and well-being. The situation can be further influenced by geographic and climate factors, household characteristics, gender, health, and age. It is therefore clear that some social groups are more prone or at risk of being or falling into energy poverty conditions. As such, households with higher energy needs, due to inhabitants by persons with disabilities, are more susceptible to energy poverty and to its effects. People with health disabilities and/or with critical dependence on electrical equipment for health reasons, are a group at risk of experiencing energy poverty.

The resolution by the European Disability Forum (EDF), indicates that 15% of the total population in Europe suffer from physical impairments and approximately 24% of persons with disabilities are at risk of experiencing energy poverty.

Even though the concept of disability is very broad, with a wide range of impairments, all disabilities present challenges for daily life.

Common well-recognized trends exist among **disabled people** and have clear energy implications:

- Some disabled people will have **specific needs** to use energy: higher room temperature, use of electrical equipment or access to a car;
- People with disabilities travel less and therefore tend to spend **more time at home**, requiring higher amounts of energy in a continuous manner (24 hours a day, 7 days a week, 365 days a year).

Economic and social difficulties generally lead to lower energy use among disabled households, not necessarily by choice. The consequences of the reduced energy consumption, including those essential for wellbeing, such as cooking and heating, are often paid for in sacrificed health creating a vicious circle. Addressing the needs of this group can interrupt the vicious circle of aggravating health conditions as a consequence of unhealthy household conditions due to energy poverty.

As such, there is a clear need **for developing tailored activities** and measures that target households that are concurrently disabled and energy poor.

Combining energy poverty with physical disability adds a layer of complexity both in terms of knowledge and **skills needed** and in terms of a **multi-actor collaborative approach**. It requires a comprehensive approach based on the understanding of the unique needs and challenges faced by affected individuals for the design of policies aimed at reducing energy poverty and promoting inclusion for the purpose of creating a more inclusive and equitable society.

When aiming to understand and tackle energy poverty for people with physical impairment, three are the main actors, each characterised by specific role and responsibility, to take into consideration:

1) Policy actors at local level, referred as **local governments**, are called to take action and address the underlying root causes of energy poverty in the framework of a fair and just transition to ensure that no one is left behind. They are responsible for shaping the policies and regulations that influence energy access, affordability, and sustainability and designing the relative policy plans (within a multilevel governance structure).

2) Actors on the ground, also referred to as **intermediaries**, are in the frontline to assist people within specific sectors, such as financial, health, social. They may also provide advice and support on energy poverty as they are well-placed to have direct and trusted dialogue with those experiencing energy poverty (who have very high trust barriers) and also possess the empathy and soft skills to discuss and provide support on various issues.

3) **People living in energy poverty** conditions that are not able to fully satisfy their energy needs and can be divided into various segments according to the level of energy poverty, ranging from at risk of falling into energy poverty to deep energy poverty. People living in energy poverty often face significant barriers that can hinder their ability to access affordable and reliable energy services. These may vary depending on the specific context, location, and the individual's level of education and awareness on domestic energy consumption, the energy market, the capacity to consume in a more efficient manner, the financial means and the ability to invest. An additional level of complexity arises for families experiencing energy poverty and **having a member with physical disability** at home, which exacerbates an already critical situation. They may require additional energy consumption, particularly if they rely on energy-powered medical devices or have to maintain specific temperature conditions. Further, the financial burdens are intensified as a large part of the income is spent on health-related aspects. And there are no qualified and competent intermediaries to refer to.

4. Mentorship

ASSERT aims to better understand the possible measures and actions to tackle energy poverty, specifically for households with members having physical impairments. ASSERT partners will thus support 25 different realities (across 5 countries) for up to 18 months through a dedicated mentorship.

The goal is to develop local skills and knowledge, to collect additional information and insight and to pilot effective local actions that can serve as further inspiration for other local governments that aim to undertake similar processes.

This process of mentorship refers to the provision of specialized support, guidance and expertise to a team of a local government and an organization (NGO, DPO,...) to help address energy vulnerability amongst people with physical impairments.

Through an open call, ASSERT will select a series of different realities to pilot this approach and co-design training material that will be useful to share the knowledge with other stakeholders.

In the next sections, we will go through the different steps of the request for mentorship, the selection process and the development of the mentorship itself.

THE MENTORSHIP PROCESS

The call for mentorship is designed to support local governments together with intermediaries' organizations to better address vulnerable consumers with physical disabilities. The graph below summarizes the development of the mentorship from the proposal submission until the end.

Figure 4 - Annex The mentorship Process

1 Pre-applications

Local governments and intermediaries' organizations will have access to the documents in their original language and get familiar with the needed information. The material is accessible on the ASSERT page. Applicants are encouraged to read the available material and understand better the overall topic.

Additional information is available at the following links [links to adapt if there is something available in national language]:

- On energy poverty – [Energy Poverty Advisory Hub](#)
- On people with disabilities - [European Network for Independent Living](#)

Different webinars are scheduled in the targeted countries and will be in the national languages: [include information and link to your national webinar]

All the resources mentioned, the video of the webinar and the presentation will be available for consultation on ASSERT Website and on the [Insert name on the organization in the country] partner website.

2 Application phase

After registering on EU SURVEY, the applicants will have access to the online application form (in their national language) and be able to fill the application on-line from **3rd February 2025 at 9:00 am** till the deadline:

16th March 2025, 6:00 pm, Bruxelles time (GMT+1)

After the deadline has passed, it will not be possible to submit or update an application. It is advisable to transfer all the content online and submit the proposal well in advance before the deadline in order to have the time to contact ASSERT team in case of any unexpected issue during the submission process (the contact is in Section7).

The application has to be submitted online but, to facilitate the process, you can download the different formats available, fill them offline and copy and paste the content online when finalised.

The proposals will be evaluated by internal evaluators (members of ASSERT team) based on the criteria described in [chapter 5](#).

5 proposals will be awarded in (put name of the country) based on the total scoring of the proposals.

Applicants of successful proposals will receive a confirmation email no later than 1 month after the deadline has passed and will be invited to the next step. Unsuccessful applicants will receive notification of the rejection and will be invited to access the on-line training and capacity buildings to develop their knowledge (notice that the capacity building will be accessible only from January 2026).

First meeting with the mentors

The successful applicants will be put in contact with their future mentors, members of the ASSERT team, in the case of [insert name of your country] the contact will be from [insert name of your organization].

During the first meeting there will be the chance to enter into detail on the structure of the mentorship and provide additional information about the request received.

Co-design

Local government and intermediary organizations will have the unique opportunity to work together with the ASSERT team and develop specific knowledge customized on their needs. The work done jointly will then constitute the backbone of the course developed by ASSERT that will be shared with a wider audience of stakeholders.

Moreover, local government, intermediaries' organizations and the mentors will work on the development of an effective action plan covering the different roles and responsibilities to implement dedicated actions to address the nexus between energy poverty and physical disability.

Mentorship

ASSERT mentors will support the local governments and the intermediaries' organizations for a maximum of 18 months. During the months of mentorship, the mentors will allocate a total of X hours to implement the support, the distribution of the hours will be defined jointly with the applicants during the first meeting with the mentor (above mentioned).

The mentors will specifically support the applicants on:

- Supporting the inclusion of social aspect in policies (addressing mainly the local government)
- Supporting to perform ex-ante and ex-post assessment (addressing mainly the intermediary organization)¹. To engage with the final beneficiaries and facilitate participation in the assessment there will be the opportunity to provide an energy kit (designed based on the input of the intermediaries and with the support of the mentor). -> this support is mandatory for each mentorship
- Support to design and implement specific actions. The mentor will support the applicants to implement specific actions. An example of possible specific actions is provided in the box below. In case the applicant is looking for a special support, it is advised to use the question and answer e-mail to receive more details. -> this support is under request of the applicant and can be adapted and customized during the implementation based on the additional information acquired during the entire process

[include the table with the list of possible actions – for each country to adapt]

Please note that the format of mentorship requires a continuous commitment by all the different applicants estimated around 8h/month per partner on average across the whole duration of the mentorship.

[for each country to adapt] Example of possible specific requests ed impact for the local government: [include appealing examples that underline the added value of the support]

- 1) Development of a tailored awareness campaign for people with disabilities and their families on energy efficiency measures.
- 2) Implement a peer-to-peer training to staff in already existing One Stop Shops to specifically address people with disabilities.

¹ A total of 100 ex-ante interview and 20 ex-post per country will be conducted per country balancing among the different awarded mentorship

5. Application

The applications need to be submitted on EU SURVEY before the deadline. Please note that the account used to fill the EU SURVEY on-line will be the one receiving follow-up information on the advancement of the evaluation so make sure to use an account that will stay operational for at least 1 year and that you check periodically.

An off-line version of the application form is available at this link. Applicants are welcomed to fill the form offline and proceed on-line only once finalized.

Language

Applicants can submit their application in their national language.

The application form is divided into 3 sections. In the following paragraph we will provide useful information to guide your drafting process.

4.1 Organizations

This section focuses on collecting direct information about the applicants and reference persons.

Direct beneficiaries

Each application should have a representative of:

- One local government: it is considered local government any public entity in charge of defining possible policies and measures on energy poverty and/or support to people with disabilities. This includes civil parish, municipalities, supramunicipalities etc.
- One intermediary organization: registered intermediary organizations are Civil Society Organization, Non-profit organization or any actor supporting the delivery of services to people with disabilities. Applicants are encouraged to address Disable People Organizations (DPOs) as key intermediary organizations.

Other stakeholders

Additional local government and/or intermediary organizations can be considered as indirect beneficiaries. The mentorship will be provided to the two applicants. However, applicants are welcomed to mention other stakeholders that will be functional for the implementation of the action and/or that can benefit from the action indirectly (e.g. be beneficiaries of peer to peer exchange, support outreach and replication of the actions, provide key information and data etc.)

4.2 Partners' Sections

This section should provide additional information about the applicants and their on-going collaboration.

Local government section

In this section, the local government should provide general information about the current situation. A short description of the geographical conditions with specific focus on the targeted area (if there is one specific), policies and measures in place concerning energy poverty and/or people with disabilities, indicators defined to monitor these two components, staff available and involved directly or indirectly in the mentorship. Include also any other key information that you believe can help understand the request for mentorship including on-going relevant projects.

Intermediary section

In this section, the intermediary organization should provide any general information about the organization itself such as the mission, vision, on-going activities, number of households, families, individuals supported as direct beneficiaries, needs identified. Make sure to integrate in the description and key information that can provide additional insight to understand the request for support including on-going relevant projects.

Collaboration with internal and external stakeholders

In this section, it is important to detail the on-going collaboration focusing on:

- The collaboration between the two applicants. How it is structured, when was it established, if there are specific contracts regulating the partnership and any additional information that helps understanding how both actors will implement the action
- The collaboration with other stakeholders either internal (such as other departments) or external (other organizations) especially if they will play a special role for the outreach, implementation, replication and scale up of the action

4.3 Mentorship request

This section is the core of the whole application and, as such, we welcome the applicants to give special attention to the requests and rely on the information here provided connected with the useful insight in the chapter 3 mentorship, the information and examples provided during the webinars.

In this section, it is key to provide all the needed information to understand the type of support needed for example:

- Reason of the request: why the applicants are not able to address the topic autonomously and need some external expert to mentor them
- Existing knowledge and capacities gap that they feel need to be filled in order to effectively support household with people with disabilities experiencing energy poverty
- Information about the final beneficiaries such as if they are in a specific targeted area, how many are the people that will directly benefit of the action, if they have a specific characteristic (e.g. people with hearing or visual impairment, people without a limb)
- People that will directly work on the action and time they will allocate
- How the specific actions for which support is required will impact the condition of the selected beneficiaries
- How policies and measure will be shaped taking into consideration the results of the actions
- How you plan to continue your support after the end of the mentorship

Make sure to include any additional information that can help the evaluators understand what the specific objectives you want to reach are and how the mentorship will increase the likelihood of success.

Additional documents (optional)

There are no specific requirements to submit integration documents but applicants are free to include information that can support their writing (e.g. Framework agreements between the applicants, specific policies, measures or actions plan currently in actions etc.).

4.4 Last section – self-evaluation.

Before proceeding with the submission there is a final section that does NOT constitute part of the application and thus will not be shared with the evaluators but contains key information for the ASSERT team. It is a self-evaluation section to be filled by both the local government and the intermediary organization. In this section is requested to self-evaluate (on a scale from 1 to 5) the experience on tackling energy poverty and the experience in supporting people with disabilities. Moreover, it is asked to sum in maximum 5 keywords what are the specific needs to address.

6. Evaluation

Each application is evaluated by at least two evaluators part of the ASSERT team. Only the applications submitted before the deadline will be considered.

All the proposals will be evaluated in their national language or after being translated in English².

Each country will be evaluated independently. The top 5 scored of each country will be awarded in order to have a total of 25 mentorship distributed: 5 Spain, 5 France, 5 Italy, 5 Greece, 5 Cyprus.

² In case of need of a translation, this will be done combining artificial intelligence and the revision of a native speaker.

Table 2 - Annex- Evaluation Sections

SECTION	CRITERIA	PARAMETERS
Organizations	ELIGIBILITY CHECK	YES-NO
Partners' Section	Check box on 3 elements each value 1 point Score 1-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the collaboration between the two applicants is structured and well detailed; the intermediary organization is a Disable People Organization (DPO); the collaboration with other internal and external stakeholders is well detailed and functional for the efficient implementation of the actions.
Mentorship request	Score from 1 to 7	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> The request is not clear and it is difficult to understand the objective and the impact Some of the key information are provided but it is difficult to understand how the mentorship should be developed and the possible added value Key information provided basic presentation of the needs presented Good presentation of the key information and the needs showing a clear analysis of the internal needs Very good presentation of the key information and needs, identification of a specific type of mentorship, good presentation of the potential of outreach Very good presentation of the needs and mentorship required, understanding of the potential outreach, understanding of the possibilities to shape policies and develop concrete measures Excellent and exhaustive presentation with key information on the needs of all the stakeholders (local government, intermediaries and final beneficiaries), specific mention to the outreach potential, sustainability of the actions and policy that can be implemented.

The evaluation focuses on 3 sections:

Organizations: This section is subjected to an **eligibility check**. Only application submitted jointly by a local government AND an intermediary organization will be

evaluated. In case information of any of the two entities is missing the proposal will not be shared with the evaluators to proceed in the evaluation process.

Partner sections - Collaboration with internal and external stakeholders: This section is scored between 0 and **3 points**. 0 is no information is provided and 1 point for each of the following information provided:

- The collaboration between the two applicants is structured and well detailed;
- the intermediary organization is a Disabled People Organization (DPO);
- The collaboration with other internal and external stakeholders is well detailed and functional for the efficient implementation of the actions.

Mentorship request: This section is scored from 1 to 7 according with the following scale:

- 1- The request is not clear and it is difficult to understand the objective and the impact
- 2- Some of the key information are provided but it is difficult to understand how the mentorship should be developed and the possible added value
- 3- Key information provided basic presentation of the needs presented
- 4- Good presentation of the key information and the needs showing a clear analysis of the internal needs
- 5- Very good presentation of the key information and needs, identification of a specific type of mentorship, good presentation of the potential of outreach
- 6- Very good presentation of the needs and mentorship required, understanding of the potential outreach, understanding of the possibilities to shape policies and develop concrete measures
- 7- Excellent and exhaustive presentation with key information on the needs of all the stakeholders (local government, intermediaries and final beneficiaries), specific mention to the outreach potential, sustainability of the actions and policy that can be implemented.

The minimum score is 1 and the maximum score is 10.

Each evaluator will score individually. The average of the two scores given by the evaluator will be the final score of the whole proposal. In case the two scores are significantly different, a third evaluator will be involved.

The result of the evaluation will be communicated to the applicants no later than 4 weeks after the closure of the submission. In case an awarded applicant decides to not proceed with the mentorship, ASSERT team reserves the right to re-open the evaluation list and contact the next applicant in the rank.

7. Data Protection

In agreement with the European Regulation 679/2016 that protects the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, ASSERT team will use the data provided in the proposal only for the objective of the present call for mentorship and in accordance with the principles of confidentiality, integrity, availability and authenticity adopted. The data can be shared with third parties that will manage it for the fulfilment of the purpose of the mandate of the call.

8. Question and Answers

Questions can be addressed by e-mail until the deadline of the open call but the ASSERT team does not assure a timely response to questions submitted after the 5th March 2025 at 6:00pm CET Brussels time, GMT+1.

For each country the reference e-mail to send inquiries is: [each country to fill]

For a fair and equal competition, all relevant questions received by applications will be replied through the Q&A section so everyone can see the answers.

Complains on results

Any question/complaints on the outcomes of the final results can be raised within 10 working days from the date that the notification email is sent. The ASSERT team will evaluate the complaint and give a response within another 10 working days.

9. Agreement signature

The awarded applicants will sign an agreement with the ASSERT team to confirm their interest in participating in the project by June 2025. The agreement is detailing the conditions of the participation. Thus, the pairs must agree to:

- Provide the pilot partners with the needed information.
- Participate in the project's activities detailed in this document and agreed with the mentor.
- Ensure the visibility of the project results and mentorship activities.

ANNEX II – Application form offline version

ORGANIZATIONS *(scores: no score but eligibility check)*

LOCAL GOVERNMENT (1 mandatory) [Local Government include any type of public entity from civil parish to municipalities and supramunicipalities]

Name:

Type of local government:

Reference person full name:

Reference person position:

Reference person e-mail address:

INTERMEDIARY [Civil Society Organisation; Non-Profit Organisation (NGO); DPOs; Other]

(1 mandatory)

Name:

Reference person full name:

Reference person position:

Reference person e-mail address:

[optional] OTHER STAKEHOLDERS (either local governments or intermediary organizations)

[Include mention to other stakeholders (either local government or intermediary organization) that you aim to be involved in the activities (keep in mind they will not be considered direct beneficiaries of the mentorship but indirect) and the role they will play. For each organization provide the following information: Name, Type, Reference Person, Reason of mention]

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[max 1000 characters]

Country of implementation: [ES, FR, IT, EL, CY]

PARTNERS SECTION

Local Governments section no score

[Briefly provide information about the area addressed, policies and measures in place to tackle energy poverty and designed to address vulnerable consumers especially people with disabilities. Detail if there are used indicators to monitor the situation and/or strategies and plans. Provide information if there are on-going projects either addressing energy poverty or supporting households with people with disabilities or focusing on both topics]

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[max 1500 characters]

Intermediary organization section *no score*

[Briefly provide information about the organization, mission, vision, and objective. Include information about the structure of the organization, the type of service provided and the number of people with disabilities you support, in case you are focusing your work on a specific target group provide additional information about their specific needs and any additional information that can help understanding your on-going activities and final objectives either focus on energy poverty or to support the household of people with disabilities]

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[max 1500 characters]**Collaboration with internal and external stakeholders**

[Briefly provide information about the collaboration between the local government and the intermediary organization, if there are ongoing joint actions or if it will be the first time working together. specific mention of the inclusion of DPOs as partner or as other stakeholders involved. Provide information about how you engage and collaborate with other key stakeholders (either internal or external) that can support the action]

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[max 1500 characters]

MENTORSHIP REQUEST score 1 to 7

[Provide description of the mentorship you would like to receive. Make sure to include the perspective of both the local government(s) and the intermediary organization(s). As guideline, cover the following topics:

- the reason related to the need of the external support
- knowledge and capacity building needed (distinguish between the needs of the local government, the intermediary and the final beneficiaries)
- targeted area
- number of people involved internally (both from the local government and the intermediary)
- final beneficiaries addressed (if open to all type of disabilities or targeting specific subgroups, specify the reason of such approach)
- how the actions for which you are asking support will have an impact on the condition of the selected beneficiaries
- policy and measure plan (existing or under development or yet to be started) to tackle energy poverty and how these will be influenced by the action
- policy and measure plan (existing or under development or yet to be started) to address people with disabilities and how these will be influenced by the action
- how you will continue the support]

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[2500 characters]

ADDITIONAL DOCUMENTS (not mandatory for submission)

SELF ASSESSMENT SECTION - NOT PART OF THE APPLICATION FORM AND AS SUCH NOT SHARED WITH THE EVALUATORS

Local governments identify up to 5 keywords that express your needs when addressing the nexus between energy poverty and people with disabilities - no score

1	
2	
3	
4	
5	

Local government: How you self-evaluate your experience in tackling EP

[Provide a self-evaluation of your knowledge and experience (1- just starting to understand EP; 2-basic knowledge of EP but not a specific understanding of all the implications; 3- understanding of EP and starting to implement a project/measure; 4- good understanding of EP with an ongoing project/measure related to this topic; 5- good understanding of EP, projects ongoing and concluded. This is a self-evaluation and it does not affect your score.]

1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5

Local government: How you self-evaluate your experience in supporting people with disabilities

[Provide a self-evaluation of your knowledge and experience with EP (1- just starting addressing this target group; 2-basic knowledge of the challenges but not a specific understanding of all the implications; 3-general understanding of the implication and already started working on it; 4- good understanding of the challenges and ongoing project/measure; 5- good understanding of the challenges and already implemented project addressing this target group, projects ongoing and concluded. This is a self-evaluation, and it does not affect your score.]

1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5

Additional comments on the self-evaluation [max 500 characters]

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Intermediary: Identify up to 5 keywords that express your needs when addressing the nexus between energy poverty and people with disabilities - no score

1	
2	

3	
4	
5	

Intermediary: How you self-evaluate your experience in tackling EP

[Provide a self-evaluation of your knowledge and experience (1- just starting to understand EP; 2-basic knowledge of EP but not a specific understanding of all the implications; 3- understanding of EP and starting to implement a project/measure; 4- good understanding of EP with an ongoing project/measure related to this topic; 5- good understanding of EP, projects ongoing and concluded. This is a self-evaluation and it does not affect your score.]

1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5

Intermediary: How you self-evaluate your experience in supporting people with disabilities

[Provide a self-evaluation of your knowledge and experience with EP (1- just starting addressing this target group; 2-basic knowledge of the challenges but not a specific understanding of all the implications; 3-general understanding of the implication and already started working on it; 4- good understanding of the challenges and ongoing project/measure; 5- good understanding of the challenges and already implemented project addressing this target group, projects ongoing and concluded. This is a self-evaluation and it does not affect your score.]

1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5

Additional comments on the self-evaluation [max 500 characters]

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THE TOTAL MAXIMUM SCORE WILL BE 10

ANNEX III – FAQs

1. Who is eligible to apply for the ASSERT mentorship program?

Eligibility is open to partnerships consisting of:

- **One local government** (e.g., municipalities, parishes, or supramunicipalities) responsible for policy-making on energy poverty and disability support.
- **One intermediary organization** (e.g., civil society organizations, non-profits, or disabled people organizations) supporting services for individuals with disabilities.

Additional stakeholders can be mentioned as indirect beneficiaries, but the mentorship will focus on the two main applicants.

2. What is the budget allocated to successful applicants?

Successful applicants will not receive budget from the project nor from the mentoring partners.

3. What is the application timeline?

The application period runs from **February 3, 2025 (9:00 am)** to **March 16, 2025 (6:00 pm CET)**.

4. What is the expected commitment for participating entities?

Participating entities should allocate approximately **8 hours/month** over the mentorship, which can be up to maximum 18-month long. and engage in pre- and post-program data collection to measure impact.

Assert Consortium

Start date: 01/10/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** LIFE-2023-CET **Coordinator:** AISFOR SRL (AISFOR)